

Importance of Psychological Well-Being in Individuals' Life

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Abstract

Psychological well-being is a multi-dimensional construct that encompasses a balanced and comprehensive experience of life and is of utmost crucial with respect to how an individual adapts functions and leads a meaningful and productive life. Psychological well-being includes an individual's mental and emotional state, overall assessment of their life. Psychological well-being can be defined by proper functioning of the psychological system. Positive functioning includes six important key dimensions of psychological well-being such as personal growth, autonomy, purpose in life, environmental mastery, self-acceptance, and positive relation with others. All these dimensions of psychological well-being lead to the contribution of mental health (Ryff, 1989). It is considered a holistic concept which includes different aspects and traits of an individual's mental and emotional health. Psychological well-being is a broad concept that focuses mainly on a person's optimal functioning rather than dysfunction and psychological distress. The absence of psychological distress does not necessarily mean an individual has high psychological well-being, as high psychological well-being is all about feeling a sense of happiness and performing well (Keyes, 2002). In simpler terms, those people with high psychological well-being reports feelings of happiness, capabilities and satisfaction with life. It is therefore, linked to greater happiness, longer lifespan, and better health. An effective psychological functioning includes sense of control or mastery, meaning and purpose in life, positive relationships and personal growth. Psychological well-being is the functioning within individuals and their relationships with others. The study was carried out on a limited number of literature reviews that explore the role and importance of psychological well-being on individuals. The present study contributes to a better understanding of various dimensions of well-being and their impacts on individuals.

Keywords: Psychological well-being, Mental health, Personal growth, Quality of life, Resilience

1. Introduction:

Psychological well-being is a term that refers to a state of mental and emotional health in which a person feels balanced, positive, and fulfilled in various aspects of life. It is also characterized by a sense of resilience, happiness, satisfaction, and thereby involving the presence of positive psychological traits such as personal growth, ability to manage life's challenges effectively, and self-acceptance. In simpler terms, psychological well-being means being able to cope with life's ups and downs and having a sense of purpose and fulfillment. It includes the presence of factors that support a healthy and thriving mind and goes beyond just the absence of mental illness. Psychological well-being is nothing but the overall mental and emotional state of an individual, which encompasses various aspects of life and contributes to a person's sense of happiness, fulfillment, and functioning. It is regarded as the positive psychological state that focuses on the presence of factors that promote a healthy mind.

The concept of psychological well-being is a state of complete emotional, social, mental, and physical well-being. It is just the reflection of an individual's positivity, resilience, and ability to form a good relationship and work fruitfully and productively (Honmore, 2015). It refers to a perfect balance in all aspects of an individual's life. A person can easily deal with any kind of situation and problem that comes into their life and knows how to welcome others with a heart full of warmth, happiness, love, and affection. Psychological well-being is state where an individual feels that they have complete control over their activities and their life. People cope up with various stress and anxieties and, realize their own abilities and capabilities.

Psychological well-being is crucial concerning how we adapt and function, and whether our lives are productive and satisfying. It tells us about how people's lives are going well and balanced. Various characteristics associated with psychological well-being are such as understanding, resilience, ability to maintain healthy and positive relationships, ability to solve problems effectively, positive work attitudes, etc. People with good psychological well-being are productive in nature and they maintain good relationships and positive attitudes towards their life and as well as others. It is essential for overall health and quality of life and is a crucial aspect in prioritizing and nurturing our mental health to achieve optimal psychological well-being. Hence, the study aims to understand the role and significance of psychological well-being in individuals' lives by exploring its key dimensions and as well as their impact on overall mental health, and life satisfaction. Therefore, the findings of the study will help in guiding the individuals and professionals in promoting practices that will enhance psychological well-being.

1.1 Definitions of Psychological well-being

Most of the researchers in the field of psychology agree that well-being includes optimal psychological functioning and experience in life (Ryan, 2001). Psychological well-being can increase with consciousness, education, extraversion and age and can also decrease with neuroticism (Keyes et al., 2002). Huppert (2009) stated that “Psychological well-being is about life going well”. Some researchers have associated psychological well-being with the fulfillment of life potential and happiness (Ryan & Deci, 2008), while some have associated with personal experience of individual (Diener et al., 1999). Seligman (2002) identifies psychological well-being as a state of enjoyment and fulfillment. According to Ryff (1989) psychological well-being is characterized by positive psychological functioning into six dimensions such as positive relation, self-acceptance, personal growth, autonomy, purpose in life, and environmental mastery. Psychological well-being is therefore important in one’s life to help people to achieve self-actualization and utilize their full potential. Psychological well-being has two important dimensions which involves the extent to which people experience happiness and positive emotions, most commonly known as subjective psychological well-being. This dimension plays a crucial role in shaping an individual’s overall psychological well-being (Diener, 2000). Moreover, the subjective aspect of well-being is categorized by affirmative emotions, meaning, and engagement (Diener et al. 2010). Well-being is not just the presence of happiness and absence of disease, but it is a complex combination of an individual’s mental, physical, social, and emotional health factors (Creed & Watson, 2003). On the other hand, the other aspect of well-being is stated as a concept that is linked to the development of human potential. In this case, it is referred to as psychological well-being (Bharathi et al. 2015). In simple terms, psychological well-being is linked to life satisfaction and happiness, and every aspect of people’s lives influences their state of well-being.

1.2 Key components of Psychological Well-being:

Psychological well-being is considered not only the absence of mental health illness, but as a broad concept that encompasses a state of happiness, thriving, and good mental health. Happiness is the emotional state of well-being that is characterized by positive emotion. Psychological well-being refers to how a person can evaluate his/her life. This evaluation may be in the form of effect or cognitions. Mostly, people evaluate their life as either good or bad and invariably experience moods or emotions that have either positive or negative effects. Moreover, psychological well-being can be defined in terms of their own perception of their lives, as well as in terms of internal experiences of the people.

Ryff (1989) developed a model of psychological well-being that consists of six dimensions or components of psychological well-being. Each of these dimensions is described below:

- **Autonomy:** It is a person's ability and the freedom to make his/her own decisions in life and act according to their own goals and values. This aspect of psychological well-being evaluates a person's capacity to remain calm and loyal towards them. This dimension indicates a sense of self-direction and sense of independence.
- **Personal Growth:** This aspect indicates a person's commitment to continuous development, growth and improvement. Curiosity, drive for advancement and self-realization, and receptivity to novel experiences are the key factors of personal growth. Personal growth is nothing but the self-growth that one becomes aware of oneself and being persistent.
- **Self-acceptance:** It is the positive state or characteristics of a person's self-image, such as strong feeling of self-worth and self-esteem, recognition and appreciation of one's own identity. The state of acknowledging and recognizing their own limitations and abilities to accept strengths and personal faults without judgment. Self-acceptance is the act of embracing who we are, accepting ourselves, and loving the entirety of our human experiences.
- **Purpose in Life:** Providing meaning in one's life is the main aim of psychological well-being. Purpose in life can help people to organize their life, make decisions and shape their goals and influence their behaviors. It gives a sense of meaning and direction, taking charge of one's well-being, having clear goals and motivations. According to this dimension, life has a purpose and a sense of personal transcendence.
- **Environmental Mastery:** Mastery of the environment refers to adapting to one's surroundings. It is an important psychological resource that helps people to protect themselves from negative consequences and adapt to change. It is regarded as a construct in the eudaimonic perspective of well-being that focuses on living in a way that encourages the expression of one's potential. A person's ability to make use of the available resources of the environment and change or create new environment when needed (Ryff & Keyes, 1995).
- **Positive Social Relationship with Others:** This dimension emphasizes mainly on the quality as well as strength of an individual's interpersonal relationships. It

promotes healthy relationships with family, friends, and the community at large. The most essential components of these dimensions are emotional support and positive social connections.

These mentioned components of psychological well-being are also known as eudaimonic well-being. It is referred to as a purposeful aspect of psychological well-being. On the other hand, hedonic well-being is referred to the subjective feelings of happiness. It is defined by two most emotional components that include high positive affect and low negative affect and as well as a cognitive component that is said to be life satisfaction. We can say that when an individual experiences strong positive emotions along with high life satisfaction then they are said to be happy. The multidimensional and broad concept of psychological well-being includes an individual's overall satisfaction with life, positive feelings, and low levels of negative emotions (Diener et al. 1999).

1.3 Importance of Psychological Well-being:

Psychological well-being, also known as mental well-being implies the state of functioning and optimal mental health. It is an utmost important factor for individuals as well as for society. As we all know psychological well-being and mental health are both interconnected. Individuals are less likely to experience mental health issues such as depression, frustration, anxiety if they are having good psychological well-being. This will help them to cope up with situations, overcome challenges, and promoting mental health. Psychological well-being is also related with success and productivity in various aspects of life. If individuals are mentally healthy and well, they are more focused and resilient towards works and ultimately resulting in positive performance and achievement. Psychological well-being improves resilience as resilience is important in adapting to difficult and challenging life experiences, promoting mental health even in the challenging situations. It also helps in enhancing emotional intelligence and leading to managing and understanding their own emotions and the emotions of others, reduces conflicts and improves relationships. Moreover, psychological well-being is indeed important in improving the quality of life. Those individuals with good psychological well-being experiences better life satisfaction and happiness. Psychological well-being has a crucial impact on relationships. Individuals maintain a healthy relationship with others, and communicate effectively in the society.

Therefore, psychological well-being is considered as paramount as it helps contribute to a balanced and healthy life of an individual, enhancing resilience, promoting emotional intelligence, and quality of life, improving productivity, and fostering good positive

relationships. In simple words, psychological well-being is important for fulfilling a healthy life, impacting mental health, and influencing overall life satisfaction and happiness. High psychological well-being is linked to lower risks of disease, improved quality of life, and enhanced resilience.

2. Review of Literature:

Gale et al. (2013) stated that, “Well-being arises from the meditation between sickness and health, which is determined by environmental variables and that are regulated by personality.” Various researchers have proposed various studies relating to psychological well-being and its factors. Akhter (2015) focuses on identifying the gender differences in psychological well-being of students and revealed that there was a large gender gap in students' reports of their emotional health. Arslan (2023) studied on psychological well-being and mental health of youth and aimed to explore the relationship between psychological well-being and mental health issues among Turkish young people. There exist lower positive psychological states in young people with internalizing and externalizing problems as compared to those without such problems. Moreover, the study recommends mental health providers in designing more interventions in order to enhance the psychosocial adjustment of students. Also, Bewick et al. (2010) reported that the psychological well-being of students changes significantly over time during the first year at university. The study showed that students' psychological well-being decreased from the start of the programme to the first year, and that gradually increased in the second year. Bharathi H. et al. (2015) demonstrated on identifying the psychological well-being of men with type 2 diabetes with the main purpose to make comparison between those with and without foot complications. Akhter (2015) in the study opined a substantial difference in age, waist-to-hip ratio, and postprandial sugar levels between the two groups. Diabetes and energy levels with foot issues showed a negative association in males. Age showed a significant correlation with positive well-being in the group without foot problems. Age and energy levels were negatively correlated and on the other hand, anxiety levels and postprandial blood sugar levels were positively correlated. Furthermore, Bhat (2018) gave importance on psychological well-being of adolescents in relation to school environment and place of living. Chaudhry & Chhajer (2023) reported that there was a significant difference between rural and urban students on the psychological well-being i.e. rural students' experiences higher psychological well-being than urban students. Moreover, there was an insignificant difference between private and government school students in relation to their psychological well-being. The researchers have also conducted another study on enhancing psychological well-being of

school teachers in India with the purpose to examine the impact of thriving, stress and energy management on the psychological well-being of school teachers suggested that there was a positive impact of energy management on psychological well-being, and a mediating effect of stress and thriving on the relationship between psychological well-being and energy management. While, Bhosale (2014) investigated on the subjective aspects of women's well-being across different occupational groups. The main aim of the study was to identify variations in positive and negative effect, overall functioning among working women, and as well as life satisfaction. The findings revealed that women who were working as administrators resulted the lowest levels of satisfaction, and on the other hand those in the medical and teaching professions experienced the highest levels of overall satisfaction. Moreover, the workplaces of working women seemed to operate as protective factors despite of the inherent difficulties that they face daily. In the study of Clark et al. (2012) revealed that the association between age and life satisfaction is described as an inverted U shape. As a result, there exists highest level of well-being in both young and older adults as compared to those of mid-life individuals. Similarly, in the studies of Creed et al. (2003) there was no significant differences in psychological well-being across age groups such as young age, middle age and mature-age in case of age factor. Dadhania (2015) examined the psychological and emotional well-being of young boys and girls. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in both psychological and as well as mental well-being of both adolescent boys and girls. Moreover, it can be seen that there was a positive correlation of 0.82 established between the two variables. However, Dhanabhakya & Sarath (2023) conducted a systematic literature review on psychological well-being and attempted to gain theoretical knowledge about psychological well-being. According to the researchers, psychological well-being is regarded as the significant factor for maintaining good mental health and is linked to enhance longer life expectancy. Hernandez et al. (2018) studied on psychological well-being and physical health. According to the researchers psychological well-being is the key element in the effect of psychology on physical health. The main issues to be noted in their studies were the conception and measurement of psychological well-being, implementation of randomized trials testing interventions to increase psychological well-being, inclusion of plausible mediators and moderators etc. Honmore & Jadhav (2015) conducted a study that aimed to explore the various aspects of psychological well-being of college going students. The study comprises of 200 first-year students (100 male and 100 female students) from various colleges in Islampur and Sangli, Maharashtra. By applying the Optimistic Pessimistic Attitude Scale (Parashar, 1998) and the

Psychological Well-Being Scale (PWB), which includes five subscales, data was gathered respectively. The findings showed that in the mental health dimension, the male students exhibited a higher level of psychological well-being compared to their female counterparts. Furthermore, in the study, most of the students belong to rural or semi-urban backgrounds that were characterized by constraints on women and entrenched traditional norms within a predominantly male-dominated culture. Jacob & Babu (2021) investigated on psychological well-being and job satisfaction among teachers with the purpose to examine the relationship between psychological well-being and job satisfaction among college and school teachers. A sample of 58 teachers (28 school teachers and 30 college teachers) was selected for collection of data. The findings of the study showed that there was a significant relationship between psychological well-being and job satisfaction among the teacher. Also there exist a significant relationship in psychological well-being between college and school teachers, a between both college and school teachers were found. A different type of study by Moghe & Mishra (2024) on Psychological well-being among University students revealed that there was no significant differences in the psychological health of both males and females, no significant differences in the factors affecting psychological well-being between male and female students, between day scholars and hostel dwellers. Similarly, Ramdas (2019) demonstrated on psychological well-being and stress among college teachers with the aim to compare the psychological well-being and stress. The sample of the study constituted of 80 college teachers (40 male and 40 female teachers) from senior colleges with an age group of 38-55 years, in Ahmednagar city. A purposive sampling technique was used and testing tools such as Psychological well-being scale developed by Sisodia & Choudary, and Social Readjustment rating scale by Holmes & Rahey were applied. The findings showed a significance differences between psychological well-being and stress among college teachers. However, stress of male teachers was found to be higher than the female college teachers, while the level of psychological well-being was higher in female college teachers than those of male teachers. In order to reduce stress and increase psychological well-being of teachers, the research suggested some stress reduction training programmes and interventions. In similar studies done by Rehman et al. (2016) on 100 Kashmiri residents (50 men and 50 women) from Ganderbal and Srinagar revealed that an unhealthy association exists between compulsive Internet usage and one's overall psychological health. The findings also revealed significant differences in the individual's psychological well-being. It resulted that there were differences in psychological well-being between both male and female adolescents, and the female youth resulted in higher levels of psychological well-

being. Similarly, teens residing in urban area performed better than their rural counterparts in terms of psychological well-being. Roslan et al. (2017) attempted to identify the level of psychological well-being among the postgraduate students from the various program in the faculty of educational studies from the University Putra Malaysia. The findings of the study revealed that there were differences in students' psychological well-being across age groups and field of study. The students of Master of Education experienced a slightly high level of psychological well-being and the students belonging to the age group 41 years and above experienced the highest level of psychological well-being. Accordingly, a study conducted by Ryff & Keyes (1995) suggested that the dimension of personal growth is decreasing in case of elderly people. They stated that autonomy and mastery of environment increases along with age. The study also showed that positive relationships with others and self-acceptance seemed to be constant at all ages, and these dimensions of psychological well-being were not affected by age. Similarly, a study conducted by Ludban et al. (2015) reported that there were age differences between students of age 18-23 years and students of age 24 years and above. In case of age and psychological well-being, a study was carried out by Panahi et al. (2013) among postgraduate students at the UPM focused on determining the level of psychological well-being among postgraduate students. The study reported that there exist a significant relationship between psychological well-being and age, and resulting that the level of psychological well-being of students increases with increase in age. The study also revealed that in terms of autonomy, purpose in life and personal growth dimensions, a significant relationship between age and psychological well-being was found. Waghmare (2016) investigated a study to examine the impact of gender and location of college students on psychological well-being. The sample of the study consisted of 100 college students from Jalna city. A Psychological Well-being Scale by Bholge & Prakash (1995) was administered for collection of data. It was found that there were no significant differences between female and male, rural and urban college students on psychological well-being. Garg & Kamboj (2021) investigated the extent to which intrinsic factors such as emotional intelligence and resilient character traits influence the psychological well-being of school teachers. The researchers believed that predictor of psychological well-being among factors of resilient traits emerged as inconsistent, but still an important mediator between psychological well-being and emotional intelligence of teachers. It was found that female school teachers showed higher emotional intelligence and resilience as compared to the male counterparts. On the other hand, Yaghoobi et al., (2019) opined that psychological well-being is the important task for the educational

professionals and directors. The main aim of this study was to understand psychological well-being which was based on psychological capital, and need for cognition among the students. As a result, psychological well-being had a significant positive correlation with psychological capital.

However, the main purpose of the present research study is to provide a broad picture of psychological well-being and its influences on human life. To understand how to achieve psychological well-being one must first require consideration of motivations, behaviors, cognition, and spiritual factors which contribute to psychological well-being. According to the perspectives of various studies, psychological well-being is not just an absence of any illness and psychological disorders, but it is more of being happy, and finding pleasure and meaning in life. It is regarded as a eudaimonic concept that focuses on the importance of personal growth, purpose, and self-realization (Niemic 2014). Most of the researchers have found that individuals with high psychological well-being were less likely to engage in drugs and alcohol consumption, and criminal activities. Few researchers thought that there was a negative impact on psychological well-being because of the exposure to work-related stress for a longer period. It leads to a lower level of psychological well-being, which in turn results in serious illness, including problems with blood sugar control, cardiovascular disease, etc (Chandola et al, 2008). Singh & Mansi (2009) focused on psychological well-being that it is considered as the subjective feeling of happiness, contentment, and satisfaction with life. Findings revealed that psychological well-being was closely related to feeling of happiness, contentment, and life satisfaction. Furthermore, Koller & Hicks (2016) examined the psychological qualities of mental health professionals and results showed significantly higher score on positive psychological capital attributes of optimism, a significantly higher score on psychological well-being especially in the aspects of personal growth, environment mastery. Similarly, Shahina & Parveen evaluated on psychological well-being of adolescents with reference to personal growth and meaning in life and found that there was a significant relationship between psychological well-being and meaning in life, personal growth initiative among adolescents' students. Hence, both personal growth and meaning in life resulted as key determinants of psychological well-being.

2.1 Research Gap:

Although many of the studies conducted and have examined psychological well-being in different groups, but it can be seen that most of them focused on specific dimensions including gender, age, occupation, or health conditions. Limited studies provided a holistic and integrated understanding of psychological well-being which includes emotional, behavioral, cognitive, and as well as spiritual aspects all together. Therefore, it can be found that there is a lack of research studies conducted which explains as a whole how psychological well-being influences overall human life.

3. Methodology:

The present study is entirely based on secondary data that was collected from published research articles, books, theses, reports, and from reputed databases. No primary data was collected for the study. Relevant literature studies were identified by using academic databases such as ResearchGate, Google Scholar, PubMed, Shodhganga, JSTOR, and also university repositories.

4. Discussion

Various studies significantly highlighted that psychological well-being is a multifaceted construct which is not just influenced by psychological and demographic variables, but also environmental and social variables. Research studies collectively showed that psychological wellbeing varies across gender, age, living environment, and occupation. Similarly, educational context and occupational context has also emerged as an important factor of psychological wellbeing. Teachers and students have also experienced fluctuating levels of well-being which were influenced by stress, job satisfaction, and academic transitions. Studies have also observed that positive psychological resources such as optimism, emotional intelligence, and resilience have contributed in higher psychological wellbeing. Furthermore, it can be said that the relationship between physical and psychological health serves the holistic nature of well-being. Studies suggested that people with higher psychological well-being maintains a better physical health outcome which includes improved metabolic and also cardiovascular functioning. Thus it can be seen that fostering psychological well-being has various benefits for maintaining both physical and mental health. Overall, the findings stated that psychological well-being is influenced by multiple interacting factors. Therefore, improving psychological wellbeing requires a comprehensive approach that integrates cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and environmental dimensions. Hence, one must promote resilience and self-growth which will ultimately serve as an effective pathway in achieving sustained psychological well-being.

5. Conclusion:

It can be concluded that well-being is the mental state of expression of positive emotions of functioning positively, social and psychological functioning (Clark et al. 2012). Psychological well-being is the most important element for the overall growth and development of an individual. The concept of psychological well-being is multi-faceted as it encompasses various aspects of an individual's physical and mental health, personal growth and development, self-esteem, maintaining positive relationships, etc. Different researchers have come up with different studies and proposed various definitions regarding psychological well-being. It is very helpful for people in order to live a healthy and meaningful life where any illness or disease is absent. Moreover, psychological well-being is said to be a major component of mental health, and individuals with higher level of psychological well-being are tend to experience a better quality of life, lower mortality risk, cope with depression and stress, better and healthier life.

Psychological well-being is the utmost important aspect in promoting good mental health. By engaging in different activities that can help in promoting personal growth and development, one can lead a meaningful and healthy life. They can enhance their well-being by seeking support from mental health providers and taking a holistic approach to promoting mental health. As psychological well-being is of growing concern in the present society, there are need to undertake proper initiatives by Government agencies, school and college authorities, etc to address the issues relating to psychological well-being.

In the present study, a limited number of literature have been discussed regarding what actions and measures can be taken at the individual level to enhance psychological well-being. Moreover, several studies have explored the factors associated with individuals' psychological well-being. Furthermore, the study aims to provide a theoretical understanding of dimensions which improves the psychological well-being of individuals and as well as the importance of psychological well-being in an individual's life.

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